

ANODIC PHENOMENA IN THE ELECTROLYSIS OF SILVER SALTS. PART I. FORMATION OF SILVER PEROXYNITRATE

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A study has been made of the phenomena at the anode when aqueous silver nitrate solutions are electrolysed between platinum and gold electrodes under different current-potential conditions.

Decomposition and anode discharge potentials have been determined for solutions of different concentrations, both in neutral and acid solutions, and at different temperatures. Current-potential curves are quite smooth and continuous in all cases.

The results of the analysis of the anodic product, prepared under a variety of conditions, show that it has, whenever formed, the same composition corresponding to the formula $\text{Ag}_7\text{O}_8\cdot\text{NO}_3$.

The following mechanism is suggested for the formation of the peroxy-nitrate. The nitrate radicals liberated on the anode immediately react with silver ions to form simultaneously Ag^{2+} and Ag^{3+} . This is quickly followed by $\text{Ag}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{AgO} + 2\text{H}^+$ and $2\text{Ag}^{3+} + 3\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{Ag}_2\text{O}_3 + 6\text{H}^+$, and AgO with Ag_2O_3 forming a complex $\text{AgO}\cdot\text{Ag}_2\text{O}_3$ and then two of the complexes $\text{AgO}\cdot\text{Ag}_2\text{O}_3$ imbibing one molecule of AgNO_3 to form $\text{Ag}_6\text{O}_8\cdot\text{AgNO}_3$ or $\text{Ag}_7\text{O}_8\cdot\text{NO}_3$.

The brownish black crystalline product, formed on a platinum anode during the electrolysis of silver nitrate, is commonly referred to as silver peroxy-nitrate. The composition of the product has been the subject of numerous investigations. There appears to be a good measure of agreement that its composition corresponds to $\text{Ag}_7\text{O}_8\cdot\text{NO}_3$. Noyes *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937 59, 1326) were able to show that this product was formed on the anode even in the presence of free nitric acid in the solution. An extraordinary observation made by Kappanna and Talati (*this Journal*, 1951, 28, 417) that a paramagnetic oxide of the composition AgO_2 is formed at the anode in the electrolysis of silver fluoride solutions, has stimulated further investigations on anodic phenomena in the electrolysis of silver salts in this laboratory. The present communication deals with the results of an investigation undertaken to determine the following :

1. The current potential conditions for the formation of peroxy-nitrate.
2. The composition of the product under different conditions.
3. The influence of the presence of acetone and alcohol in the electrolyte on the formation and composition of the anodic product.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experiments were carried out in beakers of 250 c.c. capacity, using platinum electrodes; a few experiments were carried out with gold electrodes also. The electrolyte, silver nitrate solution, was kept stirred by an electrically driven stirrer. Current was drawn from lead accumulators and regulated by rheostats, micro or milliammeters having been included in the circuit.

Decomposition and discharge potentials were measured with the aid of a precision potentiometer. A saturated calomel element with saturated ammonium nitrate bridge was used as a reference electrode for single electrode potential measurements.

Table I shows the decomposition and anode discharge potentials of solutions of different concentrations at different temperatures. The anode potentials are with reference to hydrogen electrode zero.

TABLE I

Solutions.	Temp.	Decomp. potential.	Anode discharge potential.
N-AgNO ₃	25°	0.715	1.476
	50°	0.706	1.446
	60°	0.700	1.426
	70°	0.690	1.326
N/10-AgNO ₃	25°	0.765	1.486
	50°	0.725	1.446
	60°	0.680	1.406
	70°	0.625	1.364
N/5-AgNO ₃ + N/5-HNO ₃	25°	0.975	1.656
N/20-AgNO ₃ + N/20-HNO ₃	25°	0.950	1.656
N/40-AgNO ₃ + N/10-HNO ₃	25°	0.925	1.626

It will be observed that decomposition potentials and anode discharge potentials fall with increase in temperature. The addition of free nitric acid raises both these properties. The decomposition and discharge potential curves were in all cases found to be continuous and smooth and did not reveal any abnormality, indicating that the reactions on the anode were purely secondary, following the primary discharge of nitrate ion. Detailed and repeated studies were made to see if any breaks, either in the impressed current-potential or anode current-potential curves, above the decomposition potential or anode discharge potential, could be observed with a view to determining any particular current density or potential at which the anodic deposition of the complex compound commenced, but without any tangible result. Close observations were next made just at the discharge potential point, maintaining the current and potential constant. The current passed in several cases was very small, in the neighbourhood of 36-50 microamperes. The chemical effects at the anode were sufficiently slow and could be followed visually. The bright platinum anodes first turned dull and then slightly yellowish. The yellow gradually turned into red, brown and brownish black. The change in colour is in all probability due to change in the size of the crystals and the thickness of the deposit.

Preparation and Analysis of the Product.—The appearance of the product depended upon the current density. At comparatively low current densities, the deposit looked smooth and uniform. At higher current densities, the crystals grew in size rapidly and the tendency to grow into long needles at certain places in preference to others was observable. In all cases the deposit was beautifully crystalline and adherent. It was only at later stages, when the needle-like crystals became sufficiently long, that any tendency to fall off from the electrode became noticeable.

The formation of peroxy-nitrate is accompanied by the liberation of nitric acid in the neighbourhood of the anode, and free acid lowers the efficiency of the formation of the anodic deposit. It was therefore found necessary, in order to obtain better yields, to keep freshly precipitated silver carbonate in a filter paper bag inserted in a perforated test tube, inside the electrolytic cell to maintain the solution neutral. A comparative idea of the yields under different conditions can be had from Table II. The experiments were all performed at the room temperature (30-31°).

TABLE II

Conc. of AgNO ₃ .	Current density.	Amp. hrs passed.	Wt. of deposit.	Remarks.
N/10	5.6 milliamps.	0.060	0.0184 g.	
"	13.5	0.1833	0.2044	Brisk evolution of O ₂ after 2½ hours.
0.5N	140	1.0	1.7088	Do after 1 hour.
N	140	1.0	2.6430	
N	110	1.0	3.4080	Silver carbonate in the filter paper bag.
N. at 0°	110	1.0	3.2250	Do
N. at 75°	110	1.0	1.3800	Do
N. at 30°	110 (gold electrodes)	1.0	2.1314	

The results in Table II indicate clearly that the current efficiency is dependent on : (i) current density, increasing with increase in current density ; (ii) concentration of silver ion in solution, increasing with increase in concentration ; (iii) it is practically independent of temperature between 0° and 30°, while at higher temperatures, as found at 75°, it diminishes considerably ; and (iv) on the neutrality of the solution, being considerably enhanced by the solution being maintained neutral by the suspension of silver carbonate.

Composition of the Compound.—Earlier workers* including Noyes *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) attributed the formula Ag₂O₈.NO₃ to the complex formed on the anode. In the present investigation, the analysis of the compound prepared under different conditions has been carried out for the percentages of silver, NO₃ radical and available oxygen.

Silver was estimated volumetrically by the thiocyanate method. Available oxygen was determined by reduction with ferrous sulphate in acid (H₂SO₄) solution. Nitrate was estimated as nitron nitrate after decomposition of the compound with boiling H₂SO₄ (dii.). Table III records the results of analysis.

TABLE III

Sample (Table II)	...	1	2	3	4	5	7	8	Ag ₂ O ₈ NN ₂
Ag (%)	...	80.13	79.90	79.70	79.20	79.40	80.01	79.10	79.92
**Available oxygen (%)	...	...	...	8.11	7.80	7.43	7.66	...	8.456
NO ₃ (%)	...	...	...	6.90	7.02	6.85	6.95	...	6.557

*References to earlier workers are to be found in the papers by Noyes *et al.*

**At the suggestion of the Editor the percentage of available oxygen was determined by the iodide oxidation method (estimating the liberated iodine) in dilute sulphuric acid solutions. Practically identical values were obtained.

These results definitely indicate that the composition of the anodic product formed under a variety of conditions is practically the same. Further, the analytical figures lend support to the formula $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{NO}_2$, suggested by earlier workers.

Influence of Alcohol and Acetone.—Alcohol and acetone are good solvents for silver nitrate, and observations regarding anodic reactions in the electrolysis of this electrolyte in these solvents have not been recorded in literature. Experiments were therefore carried out first with anhydrous ethyl alcohol and acetone. In both these solvents no solid silver compound was found to be deposited on the anode. Experiments were next repeated with mixtures of alcohol - water and acetone - water.

In aqueous alcohol solutions the formation of peroxy-nitrate is completely suppressed until alcohol concentration becomes very small. Even in a 3.125% alcohol solution, only a small amount of the solid is formed. The suppression of peroxy-nitrate formation is accompanied with the formation of copious quantities of the oxidation products of alcohol, viz., acetaldehyde, acetic acid and even carbon dioxide.

In the case of aqueous acetone solutions, however, the suppression of peroxy-nitrate formation is much less probably because acetone is much more difficult to oxidise. The results are summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Conc. of electrolyte = $N\text{-AgNO}_3$. Current density = 110 milliamps / cm^2 .
One ampere-hour current passed in all cases.

Solvent.	Wt. of deposit.	% Ag in deposit.
3.125% Alcohol	0.11 g.	78.88
95 % Acetone	0.70	79.10
75 % "	2.10	80.20
50 % "	2.55	79.40
25 % "	3.10	78.80

The figures in the last vertical column leave no doubt regarding the composition of the anodic product. Apart from the question of the current efficiency of its deposition, the product is the same as in the absence of alcohol and acetone.

Mechanism of the Anodic Reaction.—It has been observed earlier in the paper that the anode discharge potentials and the current-potential curves indicate that any reactions observable on the anode seem to follow the primary discharge of nitrate ions. The formation of higher valence silver compounds could therefore be due to reactions between free nitrate radicals and silver ions, probably according to the mechanism :

Followed by

Ag_2O_4 may be regarded as $\text{AgO} \cdot \text{Ag}_2\text{O}_3$ complex and two such complex molecules together seem to imbibe one AgNO_3 , forming the complex $(\text{Ag}_2\text{O}_4)_2 \cdot \text{AgNO}_3$.

All these reactions obviously take place rapidly and heterogeneously on the anode. The formation of the solid anodic product is undoubtedly due to the presence of a large number of water molecules surrounding the anode, favouring the hydrolysis of higher valence silver ions, and the absence of easily oxidisable substances like alcohol. The heterogeneous reaction between Ag^{2+} or Ag^{3+} and alcohol would thus appear to take place more rapidly than the hydrolytic reaction, as even 5% alcohol is quite sufficient to suppress peroxy-nitrate formation.

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